

THE EFFECT OF SEED IRRIGATION METHODS ON THE QUANTITY OF WASTE PARTICLES IN SOILS SUBJECT TO IRRIGATION EROSION

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Abstract: The article provides information on water conservation in egyptes when irrigating cotton on soils prone to irrigation erosion, determining the effectiveness of irrigation techniques in the fight against erosion, and the effect of cotton irrigation methods on the amount of washed soil particles.

Key words: Soils subjected to irrigation erosion in our republic, water conservation in fields during cotton irrigation, irrigation methods, soil particles, amount of leaching.

INTRODUCTION Today, 1,100 million people worldwide are affected by irrigation erosion. hectares or 56 percent of the area, including 81% of cropland in Australia, 74% in Central America, 63% in North America, 50.6% in South America, 52.3% in Europe, 59.0% in Asia, and 46.0% in Africa . Also, due to the irrigation erosion in the world, 75 bln. tons of topsoil is being lost. Due to irrigation erosion, plant nutrition and soil reclamation condition, agrochemical and agrophysical properties deteriorate, agricultural crop yields and product quality decrease.

It has been found that in cotton cultivation of the world, in order to protect the soil from irrigation erosion, as a result of raining, drip irrigation and irrigation through flexible pipes, irrigation water can be saved by 50-60%, the cotton yield will increase by 8-10 centners per hectare due to the efficient use of irrigation water and the preservation of the fertile layer of the soil. From this point of view, researches on the improvement of intensive methods of agricultural production, modern agro-technologies that save water and resources in the conditions of worsening land reclamation in the process of water shortage and irrigation erosion are considered urgent.

In recent years, in our republic, special attention is being paid to increasing soil fertility, reducing erosion processes, and developing technologies that save irrigation water. Researches on increasing irrigation erosion and reducing leaching of the fertile layer of the soil during irrigation of cotton through egate, especially in uneven terrains, are considered relevant. In the Action Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021, one of the important tasks is defined as "improving the reclamation condition of irrigated lands, rational and economical use of water resources and, on this basis, achieving the stability of production of agricultural products." In this regard, scientific research on saving irrigation water, reducing erosion processes, keeping the environment clean, and preserving the fertile layer of the soil by providing water at an optimal rate in the lands affected by irrigation erosion in our republic is considered urgent.

The purpose of the study: Irrigation consists of saving water in fields when irrigating cotton in erosive soils, determining the efficiency of the irrigation device in the fight against erosion, reducing water consumption, erosive processes, maintaining soil fertility, and growing abundant and high-quality cotton crops.

Research conditions and methods: All observations, measurements and analyzes in the research were carried out on the basis of methodological manuals "Metody agrokhimicheskix, agrofizicheskix i mikroibolicheskix issledovaniy v polivnyx khlopkovyx rayonakh", "Methods of conducting field experiments". Mathematical-statistical processing of the data obtained from field experiments was carried out using the Microsoft Excel program (B.A. Dospekhov) based on methodological manuals.

The obtained results and their analysis: It is known that under the influence of irrigation erosion, the upper, most fertile layers of the soil are washed away.

In typical gray soils subjected to irrigation erosion, when cotton is irrigated by conventional irrigation, dusty and silty soil particles are washed away from the egates through the leachate. The amount of washed soil particles varies depending on the slope of the land, the amount of water flowing in the fields, and the properties of the soil. From the results of the research, it was found that compared to the traditional method of irrigation on farms, the areas affected by irrigation erosion were washed away by soil particles when cotton was irrigated with devices for measuring the amount of water consumption. 50 slope in our experiment, (in 2011) 18.4 when the device diameter is 10 mm; 16.2 when 15

mm; When it was 20 mm, 12.6 tons of fertile soil particles were washed less, similar data were obtained in the following years.

In our experience conducted at the Central Experimental Farm of the Scientific Research Institute of Cotton Selection, Seeding and Cultivation, as a result of the observations and analyzes carried out, we can observe that the washing amount of dusty and muddy soil particles in three years depends on the methods of cotton irrigation. The obtained data showed that in the years when cotton was irrigated in the traditional irrigation method (control), an average of 29.2 t/ha of soil was washed, and 10.9 t/ha of soil was washed when irrigated with a device with a diameter of 10 mm, and with a device with a diameter of 15 mm. It was determined as a result of the analysis that 12.8 t/ha of dusty and muddy soil particles were washed away during irrigation.

It is clear from the experimental data that the rate and amount of water applied to the crop is very important for washing away the fertile layer of the soil in areas subject to irrigation erosion.

It was reflected in the data that the fertile part of the soil was preserved to a certain extent when the water distribution device was used to distribute the water at the same rate to each field during irrigation to prevent erosion of the soil fertility in the areas affected by irrigation erosion.

Summary: Reduction of erosive erosion in typical soils subjected to irrigation erosion, efficient use of water, high and high-quality production, as well as protection of the environment from agrochemicals, the use of an irrigation device with a hole diameter of more than 15 mm, its effective use, 50 dog breeders N200,P140K100 kg/ha; When it has 2.50 and 3.50 ratio, it is recommended to use refractometer as a quick method for fertilizing goose in structures of N250, P175K125 kg/ha, cleaning its water demand.

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